

BEAUTIFUL SEASONS OF THE YEAR

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Abstract. *This article provides information about interesting facts and wonders about the seasons. The article also reveals information about the seasons that you did not know.*

Keywords: *seasons, spring, summer, autumn, winter, orbit, solar system, gravity, poles*

ПРЕКРАСНЫЕ ВРЕМЕНА ГОДА

Аннотация. *В этой статье представлена информация об интересных фактах и чудесах о временах года. В статье также раскрывается информация о временах года, которых вы не знали.*

Ключевые слова: *времена года, весна, лето, осень, зима, орбита, солнечная система, гравитация, полюса.*

INTRODUCTION

Seasons - spring, summer, autumn, winter. The change of the seasons is caused by the deviation of the Earth's rotation axis relative to the plane of the orbit (the path of the Earth's rotation around the Sun) ($66^{\circ}33'$). As the Earth revolves around the Sun, the direction of the Earth's axis does not change. Therefore, as the Earth revolves around the Sun, one North Pole and one South Pole face the Sun. The Northern Hemisphere warms more when the North Pole faces the Sun, and the Southern Hemisphere warms more when the South Pole faces the Sun. Then the seasons change. The beginning of spring in the Northern Hemisphere is the time when the Sun passes through the vernal equinox (March 21-22); the beginning of the summer season when the Sun passes through the summer solstice (June 21-22); the beginning of the autumn season - the passage of the Sun through the autumn equinox (September 23) and the beginning of winter - the passage of the Sun over the winter solstice (December 21-22). The opposite is true in the Southern Hemisphere.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Seasons do not differ from each other everywhere on Earth. Mac, the weather is always the same near the equator. In the places adjacent to these countries on both sides (countries near the equator), the year is divided into 2 seasons: dry and rainy season. In the latitudes where Uzbekistan is located, the spring and autumn seasons are shorter (about 2 months), and the summer season is longer (about 5 months). In polar countries, on the contrary, summer is very short and winter lasts long.

RESULTS

Astronomical length of the seasons: spring 92.8 days, summer 93.6 days, autumn 89.8 days and winter 89.0 days, but the length of the seasons varies in different zones.

In one year, the planet Earth travels a distance of almost a billion kilometers around the Sun. The Earth's axis is slightly tilted relative to the orbit. Due to this, the Sun heats the Northern and Southern hemispheres with different powers during the year. This is the main reason for the existence of four seasons (spring, summer, autumn, winter) in our latitudes.

DISCUSSION

Winter. Winter is the coldest season of the year. It begins on the day of the winter solstice, that is, December 22. This day is the shortest day of the year. From this day on, the days will get longer and longer. In winter, many trees stop growing, some animals (for example, bears) go to sleep. Winter is one of the four seasons and is the coldest season between autumn and spring. The winter season consists of 3 months. In the Northern Hemisphere: from December, January and February, and in the Southern Hemisphere: from June, July and August. In this season, the climate level starts to fall towards minus. Because of this, cold precipitations begin to increase. Winter includes the months of December, January and February in temperate regions. The average astronomical duration of winter is 89.0 days. The days when the Sun passes through the winter solstice (December 21-22) are considered the beginning of winter. In Uzbekistan, the winter season is cold. The coldest month — January, the average temperature in the plains (Ustyurt. Churuk station) — 10° , in the southeast (Temir, Sherabad) $2-3^{\circ}$, the absolute lowest temperature in the south is -25° , -30° and in the northwest -35° , -38° . But even in the plains, there are warm days of $15-20^{\circ}\text{C}$ in winter, and $5-10^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the mountains (see Seasons). Astronomical winter lasts from December 20 to March 21 (in the northern hemisphere).

Spring. According to the astronomical calendar, spring begins on March 20. On this day, day and night are equal and it is called equinox. Then the days gradually get longer and the weather gets warmer. Plants start to wake up and bloom. Spring is one of the four seasons, and it is between winter and summer. Spring season consists of 3 months: March, April and May in the Northern Hemisphere, and September, October and November in the Southern Hemisphere. In the spring, trees begin to bud, and the weather gradually warms up. During this season, the melting of the snows that fell during the winter season and the precipitation of a large amount of rain and hail cause the filling of water reservoirs, lakes and ponds. Natural phenomena such as lightning and thunderstorms also occur most often in spring. A large amount of precipitation and some natural phenomena in the spring season cause disasters such as floods, floods and fires in some countries. Compared to calendrical spring, astronomical spring comes later, on the summer equinox (March 20 or 21 in the Northern Hemisphere, September 22 or 23 in the Southern Hemisphere) and the summer solstice (June 20 or 21 in the Northern Hemisphere, December 21 or 22 in the Southern Hemisphere).

Summer. Summer starts on June 21. In the northern hemisphere, this day is the longest day of the year, it lasts about 16 hours. This day is called the summer solstice. On this day, it occupies its highest position. Every year from June 21, the days get shorter again. In our latitudes, summer is the hottest of all seasons. Summer is one of the four seasons. Summer is between spring and autumn and is the hottest season. Summer lasts from the longest day to the equinox in the Northern Hemisphere. This season lasts from June 22 to September 22 in the Northern Hemisphere, and from January 22 to March 21 in the Southern Hemisphere. Summer is the hottest season of the year; in the temperate region (for example, in Uzbekistan) June, July, August. months Calculated. Hot half of the year among the people. It is said. The astronomical duration of the summer season is 93.6 days. In some historical sources, for example, in "Boburnoma", spring is called summer. Summer is one of the most necessary seasons for the human body. Summer season is rich in vitamin D, which is very necessary for human health and gives a great boost to the development of bones. Because vitamin D is best absorbed by the sun's rays. Sunbathing is also very beneficial for people suffering from gout.

Fruits, vegetables and other plants also begin to ripen in summer. Extremely hot summer days are harmful to human health, too much sun exposure can also damage human skin.

Autumn. Autumn starts on September 23 every year. On this day, the day and night equinox occurs again, then every day the dawn comes later, and the evening gets darker earlier. In the Northern Hemisphere, the Sun's rays fall more and more obliquely, almost "skipping" the Earth's surface. The temperature drops, the tree leaves start to turn yellow and fall. The season between autumn, summer and winter consists of September, October and November in the Northern Hemisphere and March, April and May in the Southern Hemisphere. Autumn is a season of the year. In the Northern Hemisphere, it runs from the vernal equinox (September 23) to the winter solstice (December 21 or 22). Conditionally, September, October, November are called K. At this time, it is spring in the Southern Hemisphere of the Earth. When the autumn season comes, the days are gradually getting shorter and the nights are getting longer. Cold, windy and rainy days will increase. Leaves of trees and plants begin to turn yellow.

CONCLUSIONS

These seasons last about 3 months and depend on the inclination of the Earth's axis. One might think that summer is hotter because our planet is closer to the Sun, but this is not the case. On the contrary, the distance from the Earth to the Sun is greater in summer than in winter. All this refers to the northern hemisphere. However, in winter, the sun's rays are more inclined, and the temperature is lower.

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